

Title

Integrated Temperature and Liquid Film sensors array: static characterization.

Abstract

A novel integrated sensor for the simultaneous measurement of liquid film thickness and temperature was developed and successfully characterized with respect to temperature and liquid film thickness characteristic. It consists of twenty gold electrodes for nineteen measurement points for the liquid thickness and nineteen interposed thermocouples, distributed over a length of 5.5 mm. An automated test rig for the liquid thickness calibration has been designed; it creates static liquid layers of known height with a resolution of 1.25 μm . The usable range spans from 0 to 1500 μm , measured for several liquid electrical conductivities. The influence of the electrical conductivity on the liquid film thickness measurement has been investigated as well. The temperature response was characterized in the range of 20 – 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ by means of a purposely-designed duct, in which hot air is injected. The series of thin film thermocouples also functions as alternatively as the ground electrode for the liquid film sensor. In order to use this double function for future measurements an additional driving circuit has been developed.

This type of sensor provides simultaneous spatial information of temperature and the liquid thickness. This enables real-time, spatially-resolved measurements of temperature and liquid thickness in dynamic processes such as boiling in microchannels.

1 Introduction

To date, a wide variety of applications require precise quantification of the microlayer thickness formed beneath steam bubbles nucleating on heated surfaces. This information along with the temperature can provide a more accurate estimation of the heat transfer coefficient. A significant increase of the latter can be crucial for application such as heat exchangers, heat pipes for waste heat recovery [1] or in the automotive field where the engines are now much more compact and efficient [2]. Moreover, with micro technology extending to fluidic systems, characterizing boiling heat transfer becomes extremely important for applications such as micro-reactors. Boiling induces a vapor-liquid two-phase flow, which impacts the functionalities of the micro-reactor itself [3]. Furthermore, the rapid miniaturization of electronics has led to an exponential increase in power density. In the field of chip cooling, boiling phenomena have proven to efficiently remove large amounts of heat [4]. Bubble generation has also been employed in non-cooling applications such as ink-jet printers [5], and MEMS (micro pumps and micro valves) [6].

Even though applications in microchannels offer great potential, heat transfer and in particular critical heat flux (CHF) in this context has been scarcely studied. This because of practical limitations, such as the correct assessment of temperature inside the channel, and consequently the heat flux measurement results not being reliable. Also, the heat transfer is intimately related to the liquid thickness. Qu and Mudawar [7] found that for a liquid film with a progressive evaporation in annular flow the heat transfer coefficient is obtained by the ratio between the thermal conductivity and the liquid film thickness. It must be pointed out that once the liquid thickness is known quantities such as superficial void fraction, liquid and gas velocities as well as accelerational pressure drop are easy to assess. Liquid thickness measurements at micro-scale are important but difficult, especially finding a way to be non-intrusive and accurate at such scales. The direct visualization of the flow can also help to identify the flow regime, investigate on mixing, and allow calculating the flow parameters [8], [9], but this is not always possible due to a lack of optical access.

In this paper, we present a novel sensor capable of non-intrusively measuring both temperature and liquid film thickness. This sensor array builds on the miniaturized liquid film sensors (MLFSs) previously developed by D'Aleo and Prasser [23], now enhanced with integrated thermocouples and dedicated electronics to enable simultaneous measurements. The aim of this study is to provide an initial assessment of the sensor's performance in measuring both temperature and liquid film thickness.

2 Sensor geometry

The working principle of the miniaturized liquid film thickness sensor array has been described in earlier articles [23]. The transmitter electrodes are sequentially supplied by short voltage pulses, the current read from the receiver electrodes corresponds to the liquid thickness that wets the surface in between the excited transmitter and receivers. The sensor presented in this work differs from that in [23] not only in the geometry and size, allowing for a wider measurable range of liquid thickness, but more significantly in the composition of the ground electrode. A specially designed electronic system enables this ground electrode to perform dual functions, allowing simultaneous measurement of both temperature and liquid film thickness.

Fig. 1 (a) Sensor cell top view, 1. Transmitter electrode. 2. Ground electrode. 3. Receiver electrode. (b) Thermocouple junction. (dimension in μm).

In this version, alternating arcs made of nickel and copper are connected to form thermocouple junctions exactly between the transmitters and receivers. These areas also serve as the ground electrode. (see Fig. 1).

3 Microfabrication and materials

The sensors are fabricated using a standard photolithographic technique developed for microfluidic devices. Metal layers are deposited on the substrate wafers by an electron beam evaporator and the electrode patterning is transferred using a photopositive mask. A $750\ \mu\text{m}$ thick borosilicate glass wafer of $100\ \text{mm}$ diameter is used as a substrate material. The latter is carefully cleaned and rinsed in an ultrasonic bath at room temperature using acetone followed by isopropyl alcohol (IPA), each for fifteen minutes. Afterwards, a distilled water bath with nitrogen bubbling follows. A dehydration phase on a hot plate at $120\ ^\circ\text{C}$ is necessary. A final cleaning stage uses oxygen plasma to remove any trace of organic compounds. To further improve photopolymer adhesion, the substrates are exposed to an HDMS (hexamethyldisilazane) flow for 40 s. Photoresist (MicroChemicals® AZ4562) is spun at 5000 rpm to achieve a defined thickness of about $5\ \mu\text{m}$. Exposure time is set to deliver a total dose of $280\ \text{mJ}/\text{cm}^2$. The developer mixture and developing time are adjusted according to the manufacturer’s datasheets [24]. The substrates are cleaned again in deionized water and dried. With the aforementioned first photolithography step the electrode layout and contacts pads are defined (see Fig. 2a). The photolithographic mask is produced using a high-resolution printer capable of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ minimum feature size. Metals are deposited on the substrate in a vacuum evaporation chamber: first, a 20 nm of chromium adhesion layer and then 200 nm of high purity gold (see Fig. 2a). The photopolymer mask is removed by immersing the sample in acetone (metal lift-off Fig. 2a). A second photolithography step is used to create the nickel part of the ground electrode, which must be precisely aligned with the preceding pattern on the substrate. This layer comprises 100 nm of evaporated nickel, followed again by a lift-off stage (see Fig. 2b). A third photolithographic step is applied to complete the ground electrode with an evaporated copper layer of 150 nm (see Fig. 2c). An epoxy-based permanent resist is used as a protective layer (Microchem® SU-8 2002 [25]). This layer of $2\ \mu\text{m}$ serves to cover the electrodes which are not in contact with the liquid.

After spinning, the substrates are left at room temperature for 10 min, and then they are slowly heated up to 95 °C (2 °C/min) on a hot plate and kept at this temperature for 30 min. A gradual cooling to room temperature is conducted to avoid thermal shocks. The total UV dose of 300 mJ/cm² is split in six parts to avoid stressing the polymer. Post-exposure bake is needed and follows the same steps as the prebake stage. A mixture of MR600 (Microchem®) is used for the development, the samples are immersed in this solution for 30 seconds, after which they are rinsed with IPA. In order to harden the resulting structure and relax the potential thermal stresses, the polymer is slowly hard baked at 180 °C (2 °C/min) for 30 min (Fig. 2d).

Fig. 2 Microfabrication processes. (a) Gold electrode patterning, deposition, and lift-off, (b) ground electrode patterning, nickel deposition, lift-off, (c) ground electrode patterning, copper deposition, lift-off, (d) cover layer patterning, SU8 coating. 1. Wafer top view, 2. electrodes close-up view, 3. cross-section (not in scale).

3.1 SU8-2002 impedance

Fig. 3 SU8 2002 specific impedance.

To assess whether the cover layer affects the conductance measurement, the electrical impedance of a film of a processed SU8 was measured. An impedance analyzer was used with two flat electrodes placed above and below a 2 μm thick SU8 layer and the electrical behavior was assessed over the range of 1 Hz to 10 MHz. Fig. 3 shows the specific electrical impedance (per unit area and length) of a processed SU8 film. Considering that the electrodes lie on the borosilicate glass and the distance between two adjacent leads is 250 μm , the influence of the cover layer can be considered negligible, even at high-order harmonics of the 10 kHz sampling frequency (10 kHz).

4 Calibration setups

4.1 Temperature calibration setup

Fig. 4 Temperature calibration setup. (a) Isometric view, (b) side view. 1 Airflow inlet, 2 sensor plate, 3 thermocouples, 4 airflow outlet, 5 reference thermocouples location.

Two halves of a machined aluminum frame encase the sensor array, forming a circular channel around it. A temperature-controlled airflow is introduced through a single inlet. Three thermocouples in direct contact with the sensor surface serve as temperature references. Preliminary tests were conducted to verify thermal field uniformity. After steady-state conditions were reached, the maximum temperature difference measured over a 10 mm distance was less than 0.5 °C.

4.2 Liquid Thickness calibration setup

As shown in Fig. 5, the sensor plate is anchored at the base of the calibration setup. A droplet of deionized water mixed with potassium nitrate (KNO_3) is deposited on the sensitive area. A stiff plate, moved by the microstage, presses against the droplet, generating thin layers of conductive liquid. The microstage is driven by a stepper motor capable of 1.25 μm resolution.

To characterize the relationship between layer thickness and signal, and its dependence on electrical conductivity, water with varying KNO_3 concentrations was used. Three mixtures were investigated, with electrical conductivities of 300, 800, and 1140 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Fig. 5 Liquid film thickness calibration setup. (a) Isometric view, (b) side view. (1) Step motor, (2) electronic controller, (3) microstage, (4) Hall sensor for height sensing, (5) sensor, (6) stiff plate.

4.3 Data acquisition system

Fig. 6 Data acquisition scheme. (a) Block scheme, (b) timing diagram.

The ground electrode plays a fundamental role during the liquid film measurement because it absorbs part of the current that would otherwise flow to the receiver electrode. This configuration results in a wider measurement range. Near the origin, sensitivity is reduced, allowing small film thicknesses to be measured with low uncertainty. The ground electrode must be connected to the zero-potential reference (GND). To read the thermocouple voltage, each arc must be disconnected from the ground reference (GND Fig. 6). The WMS provides a synchronization signal used to control a set of triggered electronic switches (SW Fig. 6). These switches connect the ground electrodes to GND during liquid film measurements and disconnect them during temperature readings. The thermocouple signals are amplified by a set of instrumentation amplifiers (AMP Fig. 6). The amplifier set was characterized in terms of effective gain, offset, and noise performance. The gain was selected to ensure a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio and improved noise rejection. The average gain value used is 4503. The average measured offset voltage is $-11 \mu\text{V}$, which is below the maximum value reported in the amplifier datasheet [26].

5 Results

5.1 Sensor description

Fig. 7 Finished sensor. (a) Top view, (b) sensor area close-up view.

The fabricated sensor includes 19 measuring points each comprising a liquid film sensor pair and a thermocouple distributed over a length of 5.5 mm.

Fig. 8 Electrode distribution. The colors in the figure are used to reference the next plots.

A 200 μm wide slot in the SU8 layer exposes only the contact pads to the liquid, while protecting the electrical leads carrying the electrical signals.

5.2 Temperature calibration

A jet of air at a controlled temperature is injected into the test section described in section 4. Once the steady state conditions are reached, the temperature array signals are recorded. The thermocouples were calibrated in the range of 20 – 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Fig. 9 shows the average output signal at each temperature point. The standard deviation among the thermocouples signal is 1.57 %.

Fig. 9 Average temperature calibration curve.

Within the sensor's operating range the response is linear, with a correlation factor R^2 of 0.997. The deduced Seebeck coefficient is, on average $18.5 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{V}/^{\circ}\text{C}$, which is in reasonable agreement with the value calculated from bulk material properties ($11.54 \mu\text{V}/^{\circ}\text{C}$) [27].

5.3 Liquid film calibration

5.3.1 Conductivity versus temperature

Fig. 10 Electrical conductivity versus temperature, mixture of DI water and KNO_3 .

The influence of temperature on electrical conductivity was preliminarily assessed by heating a solution with a room temperature conductivity of $300 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

The curve in Fig. 10 shows a linear dependence on temperature, with a correlation factor R^2 of 0.9873. This plot will be used to estimate the equivalent temperature change corresponding to variations of the electrical conductivity.

5.3.2 Curve characteristics

Fig. 11 Calibration curves (black and dashed black traces) and cross-talks corresponding to the fifth transmitter activated ($800 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$).

Fig. 11 shows the signal strength as a function of increasing liquid thickness. The black traces correspond to the receiver electrodes closest to the activated transmitter, forming the transmitter-receiver pair (TRP). Notably, at greater thicknesses, a current signal begins to be detected by the next pair of receiver electrodes (red and dashed red traces). The thickness required to observe this cross-talk is approximately a multiple of the distance between two receiver electrodes ($500 \mu\text{m}$, $1000 \mu\text{m}$, etc.). Section 5.3.6 discusses the intensity of these secondary signals, which is important for defining the lateral influence on the TRP, particularly in the presence of a non-uniform layer, such as one caused by a slug or a wave.

Calibration curve characterization is based on the inflection point z_f of the measured signal. This point defines the thickness at which the sensor reaches maximum sensitivity, and depends solely on the sensor geometry. This coordinate has been found to be related to the distance between the activated transmitter and the receiver under investigation.

Fig. 12 Calibration curves for different electrical conductivities.

Fig. 12 shows representative calibration curves for a TRP located at the center of the sensor, for three different electrical conductivities. Higher electrical conductivity increases signal strength due to increased sensitivity. This effect has several implications for the calibration curve characteristics, including:

1. Thickness error (ϵ_z).
2. Range (Δz).
3. Asymmetry (ψ).
4. Lateral dispersion (δ).

5.3.3 Thickness error

Electrical noise in the measured signals introduces an uncertainty in the deduced thickness. To quantify this error, the following expression is used:

$$\epsilon_z = \frac{\Delta s}{s'(z_f)} \quad (5.1)$$

Here, Δs is the uncertainty due to electrical noise, and $s'(z_f)$ is the derivative of the calibration function evaluated at the inflection point.

Fig. 13 Thickness error versus conductivity.

Fig. 13 shows that the electrical noise in the apparatus induces a thickness error of less than 17 μm . Increased electrical conductivity improves the signal-to-noise ratio, thereby reducing the uncertainty in thickness estimation.

5.3.4 Range

The range of a liquid film sensor refers to the span of film thickness over which the sensor remains linear, before saturation occurs. One analytical and consistent method for determining this range is to trace a line that passes through the calibration minimum and maximum values (s_M and s_m respectively), intersecting the inflection point ($z_f, s(z_f)$) with the slope $s'(z_f)$.

The range Δz will be:

$$\Delta z = \frac{s_M - s_m}{s'(z_f)} \quad (5.2)$$

Assuming the calibration curve is normalized such that $s_M - s_m = 1$.

Fig. 14 Range versus conductivity.

Fig. 14 shows that the useful range of this sensor geometry generally exceeds 1000 μm . However, increasing the electrical conductivity steepens the calibration curve, thereby reducing the effective measurement range.

5.3.5 Asymmetry

Fig. 15 Calibration curves at 800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$.

Due to the finite dimensions of the sensor, the outer electrodes are subjected to different electrical conditions compared to those near the center. This may cause an imbalance in the TRP response (see Fig. 15). The root mean square error (RMSE) between a given calibration curve and the one at the center has been used to quantify such a deviation.

$$\psi = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^N [s_5(k) - s_1(k)]^2}{N}} \quad (5.3)$$

Fig. 16 Asymmetry for different TRPs at different electrical conductivity.

As previously noted, increased electrical conductivity improves the signal-to-noise ratio, which in turn reduces variation among the calibration curves. The RMSE remains below 0.1 across the entire calibration range (up to 2500 μm). The “Ground Electrode Wings” are clearly visible in Fig. 7b. The ground electrode has been purposely elongated to provide greater symmetry at the peripheral electrodes. This design modification also extends the sensor’s measurable thickness range.

5.3.6 Lateral dispersion

Fig. 17 Gaussian fitting along the y-direction for increasing thickness layer.

The calibration curves and cross-talk signals corresponding to a single activated transmitter (e.g. Fig. 11) were fitted along the y-direction with a Gaussian function (see eq. (5.4)). This fitting procedure was then applied to each layer, resulting in the surface plot shown in Fig. 17. Plotting the standard deviation $\delta(z)$ of these Gaussian fits provides a quantitative measure of the lateral dispersion.

$$s(y,z) = s(z) \cdot e^{-\frac{y^2}{\delta(z)^2}} \quad (5.4)$$

Fig. 18 Sensor lateral dispersion versus thickness.

The lateral dispersions for different electrical conductivities are shown in Fig. 18. It is evident that increased thickness leads to a stronger signal measured by neighboring electrodes. Despite this, the signal does not spread as much as expected because a thicker layer corresponds to lower impedance to the closest receiver. Therefore, signal dispersion to more distant electrodes decreases with increasing electrical conductivity. The lateral dispersion values were fitted with a second-order polynomial ($\delta(z) = p_0 + p_1 \cdot z + p_2 \cdot z^2$) the coefficient are reported in Tab. 1, along the R^2 values.

σ [$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$]	p_0 [$10^{-5} \mu\text{m}$]	p_1 [-]	p_2 [μm^{-1}]	R^2 [-]
300	1.16	-0.0053	506.07	0.995
800	2.32	-0.0192	505.98	0.995
1140	1.86	-0.0137	504.01	0.997

Tab. 1 Polynomial fitting coefficients.

The calibration function $s(z)s(z)$ represents the current collected by the receiver at each layer height z . It exhibits a convex behavior for thinner layers and becomes concave after passing the inflection point. This behavior suggests an opposing effect that reduces the receiver current, which is active at lower thicknesses. This loss of current is due to the ground electrode, which is purposely placed between transmitter and receiver in order to widen the thickness range. Therefore, $s(z)$ can be modeled as a combination of two similar

saturating functions such as exponentials each acting over different characteristic lengths δ_a , δ_b .

$$s(z) = a \left(1 - e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_a}} \right) - b \left(1 - e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_b}} \right) \quad (5.5)$$

Fig. 19 Comparison between experimental characteristics and fitting functions for different electrical conductivities. (a) 300 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, $R^2 = 0.983$, (b) 800 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, $R^2 = 0.990$, (c) 1140 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, $R^2 = 0.982$.

The simplified model function fits well with the calibration curves in a wide range of electrical conductivities as shown in Fig. 19. Therefore, eq. (5.4) can be completed with eq. (5.5):

$$s(y,z) = \left[a \left(1 - e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_a}} \right) - b \left(1 - e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_b}} \right) \right] e^{-\frac{y^2}{\delta(z)^2}} \quad (5.6)$$

As expected, δ_a and δ_b depends solely on the electrode geometry. The calculated average value of δ_a is 260 μm , closely matching the nominal distance of 250 μm between the activated transmitter electrode and the nearest receiver. Further support for this hypothesis comes from the δ_b fitting result of 39 μm , which closely matches the transmitter-ground electrode distance of 50 μm (see Fig. 1).

5.3.7 Signal to thickness

To retrieve thickness data from the sensor signals, the calibration functions must be inverted. A function is invertible if it is both injective and surjective. Since the calibration function saturates, it is not surjective as $z \rightarrow +\infty$; however, it can be treated as such by restricting the domain to the practical range $[0, \Delta z]$. To ensure injectivity, the calibration function must be continuous and strictly monotonic within this domain. It is continuous, as it is composed of continuous functions. Monotonicity is evaluated by analyzing the first derivative with respect to z (5.7):

$$s'(z) = \frac{a}{\delta_a} e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_a}} - \frac{b}{\delta_b} e^{-\frac{z}{\delta_b}} \quad (5.7)$$

This derivative remains positive as long as the condition in Eq. 5.8 is satisfied:

$$z < \frac{\delta_a \delta_b}{\delta_a - \delta_b} \ln \left(\frac{\delta_a b}{\delta_b a} \right) \quad (5.8)$$

For the determined values of a , b , δ_a , and δ_b the domain where invertibility holds is limited to 40 μm . This range is too narrow for practical use, so the original calibration function cannot be inverted analytically. Instead, the calibration functions are approximated by polynomial fits of the form $z = c_0 + c_1 \cdot s + \dots + c_n \cdot s^n$, which are invertible within the signal domain. The fit is applied over the range where the calibration signal reaches up to 90% of its saturation value covering more than the usable range of the sensor for each specified electrical conductivity. The resulting polynomial coefficients are reported in Tab. 2.

σ [$\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$]	c_0 [μm]	c_1 [10^3]	c_2 [$10^4 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$]	c_3 [$10^5 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$]	c_4 [$10^5 \mu\text{m}^{-3}$]	c_5 [$10^5 \mu\text{m}^{-4}$]	c_6 [$10^5 \mu\text{m}^{-5}$]	c_7 [$10^5 \mu\text{m}^{-6}$]	c_8 [$10^6 \mu\text{m}^{-7}$]	c_9 [$10^6 \mu\text{m}^{-8}$]	R^2 [-]
300	2.76	3.11	-5.56	5.57	-2.95	8.96	-161.06	169.28	-9.6	2.27	0.9805
800	-20.8	3.34	-2.93	1.52	-4.16	6.13	-4.59	1.38	-	-	0.9940
1100	-0.49	2.13	-1.58	0.87	-2.59	4.08	-3.23	1.02	-	-	0.9822

Tab. 2 Polynomial coefficients for the inverted calibration fitting functions.

Fig. 20 Polynomial fitting functions, for different electrical conductivities.

6 Conclusions

A new sensor array was developed for the simultaneous measurement of film thickness and film temperature. This article describes the fabrication process and the calibration technique of the array in terms of both temperature and liquid thickness.

The authors considered it worthwhile to report the measured electrical impedance of the negative permanent polymer SU8 first, to demonstrate that it does not interfere with the measurements, and second, to provide additional data that are not readily available in the existing literature.

The sensor consists of 19 measurement points for temperature and liquid thickness distributed over a length of 5.5 mm. It must be noted that the WMS also enables the collection of cross-talk signals, for a total of 100 measurements per frame.

Static calibration, in terms of temperature and liquid film thickness, was conducted using two dedicated setups.

Furthermore, the influence of electrical conductivity on the main performance parameters of the sensor was investigated, showing that thickness uncertainty, range, asymmetry, and lateral dispersion all decrease as electrical conductivity decreases.

Using the definitions adopted in this study, the range is approximately 1275 μm , the maximum uncertainty is 16.5 μm (for $\sigma = 300 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), and the lateral dispersion is 520 μm (measured at $z=1275 \mu\text{m}$).

The array is now prepared for further dynamic investigations, for which the derived parameters and characteristics will support improved interpretation of the measured signals.

7 References

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